

MOTI

Introduction

Moti is a mobile application that can be used to measure standing stock, tree height, tree composition, number of trees per hectare and timber stock. MOTI calculates the timber stock based on the standing stock, calculated with the Bitterlich angle counting method, and the measured standing height and shape of the trunk. The application has a built-in automatic correction of the calculation due to the slope of the terrain. The measurements of the logbook with the MOTI application are not significantly faster than manual measurements, but we save a lot of time when calculating the wood stock and transferring and processing the data, since MOTI allows immediate calculation of the wood stock in the field.

Lessons learned

Compared to classical methods of measurement, the application has many advantages. Smart devices offer ever-improving optics, contrast screens with the ability to enlarge the image, which is especially important for measurements of the existing baseline, when by enlarging the image, you can quickly find out whether a certain tree still exceeds the selected viewing angle or not. Enlarging the image is very useful even in conditions of poor visibility, when by zooming in on the image on the phone or tablet, we can quickly check what is several tens of meters away from us and whether another tree might be hiding behind the tree.

Figure 1: Overview of digital platform.

For further information contact

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Further information

<http://digigozd.si/aplikacija-moti/>

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